

A STUDY ON AWARENESS LEVEL ON CROP INSURANCE SCHEMES AND THE FACTORS INFLUENCING CHOICE OF INFORMATION SOURCES AMONG FARMERS

Dr. Y. Rajaram¹ and Chetana B.S²

¹Former Dean and Professor,
Ramaiah Institutes of Management Sciences, Bangalore

²Assistant Professor of Banking, Manipal University and
Research scholar, Tumkur University.

ABSTRACT

Agriculture is home for small and marginal farmers constituting around 80% of the agriculture community in India. The performance of agriculture growth, livelihoods and food security depends on small and marginal holding farmers. The research study is based on primary survey conducted to analyse the awareness level among crop insurance holders. It is observed that farmers are unaware of market related information. The paper reviews that there are lot of market oriented reforms which are announced by the Government which ensures level playing field in the agriculture sector. An effort is made to list out existing mechanism available to farmers in getting required information on soil health, water, inputs, credit, information, technology and markets .

Keywords: awareness on WBCIS, Crop insurance.

1. INTRODUCTION:

70% of Indian rural population depends on agriculture and over the years they are dependent on indigenous or local knowledge for improving farming system, yield etc. These local knowledge refers to skill and experience gained over many generations through traditional practices. This has not helped farmers to improve agricultural yield, besides rural India has witnessed emergence of new diseases, resistant plant weeds and pests, soil infertility due to over usage of fertilizers etc. The farmers' condition in India is very unpleasant and hence they do not want their children to continue with farming activities. Low income. Low productivity, irregular weather cycles, inadequate support from the government are the most important reasons for dissatisfaction among farmers. (Lokniti.org) (State of Indian Farmers: A Report. Delhi: Centre for the Study of Developing Societies (CSDS), Delhi. 1988).

The Finance Minister Arun Jaitley in Union Budget 2018-19, emphasized on higher income for farming community and said that the Government considers agriculture as an enterprise and will support farmers in producing more from the same land with lesser input cost

and realise higher price for the produce. As a primary measure Government has announced that Minimum Support Price to keep at least at one and half times of their production cost for all Kharif crops. ‘Operation Greens’, on the lines of ‘Operation Flood’, is expected to promote Farmer Producers Organisations, agri-logistics, processing facilities and professional management in the sector.

As a prelude to Finance Minister Strategy on agriculture and rural Development, the most important factor in agriculture is Information and Communication. Agriculture is considerably localized nature and as such information must be specially adapted to the different conditions. Farmers face lot of challenges due to changes in weather patterns, soil conditions, pests, diseases and epidemics. Time and again, there are various schemes such as crop insurance schemes, Gramina Bhandaran Yojana, Gramina Kaushalya Yojna, integrated rural development program, Mahatma Gandhi National Rural development Guarantee Act etc. announced by Government of India, but Farmers should cope with updated information.

The information related to agriculture are expected to reach farming communities through various forms such as community libraries, radio, film shows, TV, newspaper, pamphlets on agricultural, State and Local level agricultural agencies etc.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A primary survey was conducted to analyse the awareness level on crop insurance schemes among the farmers between Kharif 2012-Rabi 2014 in the state of Karnataka. The study was conducted based on Stratified -multistage random sampling technique. Total of 383 farmers from five taluqs of Haveri district were chosen as sample size. The schedule was canvassed to those farmers who had availed Weather Based Crop Insurance Scheme at-least for one season.

3. ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS OF PRIMARY SURVEY ON AWARENESS LEVEL

Farmers voluntarily choose crop insurance scheme provided they are aware of premium structure, crop insurance provider, process of availing crop insurance, claim settlement, etc.

The cognitive aspects were tested on three rating scale (i.e. Not aware=0, Aware=1 and highly aware=2). Following Eight variables were chosen to test three hypothesis.

- Objective of availing the insurance
- Name of the insurance scheme
- Amount of premium paid
- Knowledge of Insurance company
- Claim settlement process

- Application process
- Technical aspects of the scheme such as term sheet, triggers, RMS, etc.
- Calamities covered

4. HYPOTHESIS 1: THERE IS NO SIGNIFICANT AWARENESS OF WBCIS AMONG THE FARMERS.

The priori hypothesis is that 75% of the farmers are aware of all aspects of WBCIS. The null hypothesis is that 75% or more are not aware of the scheme.

Fig: Level of awareness about WBCIS among respondents

(Source: Primary survey)

In six out of eight variables of awareness, majority of the respondents are unaware of the scheme information.

Eight statements were designed in the interview schedule to measure level of awareness among the farmers who have availed weather based crop insurance scheme. Basing on the scores, all the respondents are grouped as farmers who are aware of the scheme (respondents who have scored equal to or more than eight) and farmers who are not aware of the scheme (respondents who have scored less than eight).

Table: level of awareness based on all variables

Category of response	No. of responses	Percentage of responses
farmers who are not aware of the scheme	330	86.2%
farmers who are aware of the scheme	53	13.8%

Result: 86% of farmers are unaware about the details of the scheme and hence hypothesis is accepted. It is inferred that there is no significant awareness of WBCIS among the farmers.

Name of the insurance scheme:

There are many insurance schemes being launched by the state since 1972. From year to year, these schemes are being modified to suit the requirement of farmers. In this respect, it is important for farmers to know the current insurance scheme name and main features of the scheme. But around 70% of them are unaware of either name of the crop insurance scheme nor the features. They are not in a position to differentiate between two major crop insurance schemes prevailing during the study period.

Knowledge of insurance company:

Around 88% (336) of the respondents do not know which insurance company has provided crop insurance service for the period. While interviewing the insured farmers, a few of them informed that the respective lending Bank is providing crop insurance service. They are unable to differentiate between lending Bank and insurance company, which shows the ignorance level among the farming community about the objective and concept of Crop insurance.

Objective of availing the insurance:

Majority of farmers i.e. 51% (196 respondents) retorted that the purpose of buying crop insurance. Around 20% of farmers (76 respondents) expressed that crop insurance scheme gives financial security during distressed period and it is compulsory for availing crop loan. Remaining 29% (111 respondents) are unaware of the scheme objective.

Amount of Insurance premium paid:

Only 2.1% (8 members) of respondents were able to say the amount of premium paid during the period for WBCIS and they are also able to say that premium differs from crop to crop. Around 31% (120 respondents) of the farmers know that they have paid crop insurance. However they could not tell the approximate amount of crop insurance paid for the period and they are unaware of crop wise premium structure. Around 67% (255 respondents) of farmers do not know that they have paid premium. The premium is being deducted from loan account directly and they can't differentiate between interest on loan and premium for crop insurance.

Application process:

Around 6.3% of respondents can fill the application form for crop insurance independently in the respective financial institution where they have borrowed loan within the notified period and they are highly aware of application process. Around 75% of the respondents have filled application form for availing crop insurance with the help of a banker and they are considered as respondents who are aware of application process. Around 19% of the farmers are unaware of the crop insurance form and they have just signed papers shown by the Banker. After introduction of on line application form farmers are asked to share their basic information in a small form and application form is filled by the Bank.

Claim settlement process:

Only 2% of the respondents are highly aware of the settlement process of WBCIS. They know that claims are credited to the account based on the weather triggers. And these members could differentiate between crop cutting experiment and weather parameters. Around 31% (120 respondents) of the insured farmers are aware that the claim is settled by an agency and amount is credited to the beneficiary account which will be adjusted with the amount of loan. Majority of the respondents, 67% are unaware of claim settlement process, they can't differentiate between crop cutting experiment and weather parameter based settlement. They are under impression that the settlement is done by lending banks.

Calamities covered:

Only 5 insured farmers (1.3 % of respondents) are highly aware of the various categories of natural calamities covered and the local calamities which are excluded under the scheme. They know the difference between yield based approach and weather based approach of crop insurance schemes. 76 farmers (20% of respondents) are aware that certain crop loss such as loss due to poor quality of seeds, post harvesting loss are not covered. However they did not list out perils covered under WBCIS and perils not covered under WBCIS. Majority of respondents, 78.9% (302 members) are unaware about the perils covered under the scheme.

Technical aspects of the scheme such as term sheet, triggers, RMS etc.:

Very few respondents i.e. 1.6% (6 members) are highly aware of the existence of rain gauge on the roof of Gram Panchayat office and structure of term sheet for different crops. They also know that if weather is not favoring the crop, then the weather triggers help them in getting compensation for crop loss. Around 26% of respondents are aware of the existence of RMS for determining crop loss. But these 101 respondents are unaware of the functions and purpose of RMS. Again majority of respondents 72% (276 members) are unaware of the existence of RMS, Term sheet and technical aspects of claim settlement under WBCIS.

The independent variables were also tested for their relationship with the awareness level.

5. HYPOTHESIS 2: THERE IS NO SIGNIFICANT DIFFERENCE BETWEEN LEVEL OF EDUCATION AND AWARENESS ABOUT THE SCHEME.

Fig: Level of awareness about crop Insurance scheme and Educational qualification

(Source: Primary survey)

It is observed from the above figure that 75% (6 respondents) of illiterate are unaware of the scheme. Among the insured farmers who have studies up to 4th standard of primary education around 74% (62 respondents) are unaware about WBCIS. Among 121 respondents, who have studied up to 7th standard and completed secondary education, 68% (82 members) are unaware. Similarly 50% (32 members) of farmers who studied till 10th standard (SSLC) and 51% (27

members) who studied till 12th standard (PUC), 43% (23 members) of the graduates are also unaware of WBCIS.

Chi-square test for independence was conducted to test the hypothesis to compare two categorical variables in contingency table and hypothesis is rejected. There is a significant difference between level of education and awareness about the scheme. It can be inferred that the level of educational qualification has an impact on quest for understanding and comprehending WBCIS.

6. Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference between land holding and awareness about the scheme.

Fig: Awareness about crop insurance and Land holding category

(Source: Primary survey)

Chi-square test for independence was conducted to test the sub hypothesis to compare two categorical variables in the contingency table and Hypothesis is rejected. i.e. there is a significant difference between land holding and awareness about the scheme. The special technologies used in the scheme, the technical terms used in the term sheet, the combination of agro-meteorology and statistics parameters are beyond layman’s comprehension. Awareness among large and medium scale land holders are higher than the small and marginal farmers. It can be attributed to the fact that the inhibition level of richer class is lower than among the poor and middle class farmers and as such, they enquire while paying premium in the Bank about the scheme, features, grievances cell etc. The small and marginal farmers will never seek information from anyone. A farmer who availed crop insurance without knowing about the scheme information such as perils

coverage, premium amount, application process, etc. and later if the same farmer loses crop, then he will be clueless as to what to do and how to claim for losses.

Many farmers are still following traditional method of exchanging information from face-face from extension agents. It is required to have a targeted approach to circulating agriculture-related information which will have diverse sources and can ensure information reaches all farmers. The first step to empower farmers is share basic information. Farmers face challenging situation because of uncertainty relating to climate change, climate variability. Timely information on Weather forecast, new technologies, government schemes and market prices can enable them to make better choices and decisions and they can produce more with less input cost.

Farmers are not homogeneous group. The sources of information chosen by different Socio economic group always tend to differ. Richer and educated farmers tend to use a greater diversity of information sources and more modern ICT tools like mobile phones. (Mehtar, 2015)

It is very important for the farmers to collect suitable data from concerned Department.

Thanks to GPS, Internet and affordable 4G technology, few farmers are attempting to collect data about their farms such as usage of water, inputs, crop yields, market condition, soil health etc. this data help farmers

1. To manage their operations in a better way– the more information they have, the more they can make decisions that are tailored to their farm’s specific needs.
2. To identify the efficiencies which will lead to higher productivity, higher profitability, lower input costs, and optimum utilization of fertilizer.
3. To strengthen the supply chain relationships so as to ensure supplier work with the farmer on a long-term basis.

7. The following measures are undertaken by the Government to support Farmers in ensuring flow of information:

Free SMS: A robust system developed by India Meteorological Department in association with Ministry of Agriculture to provide weather based agromet advises to the farmers. Farmers need to register with name, mobile number and crops grown during the period. On a weekly basis they will receive SMS on day to day agri operations and extreme weather events.

Raitha Samparka Kendras: The Department of Agriculture, Karnataka has established these centres at hobli level with the clear objectives of providing updated knowhow on crop production, arranging critical agricultural inputs, testing of primary soil and seed and to arrange interface between public and private sector technologies.

Help line Services: Multiple helpline services are established to give solution to all queries relating to agriculture.

National Helpline for Farmers like Bayer's national helpline. The helpline will be answered by local agri-experts from five call centers located in various parts of the country. Bayer's also offer a strong network of trade partners and the Bayer Solutions stores.

Kissan Call center: The portal is available in multiple languages like English, Hindi and other regional languages. Through this farmers can get agriculture related news, information, video tutorials of farming, crop diseases, crop management, weather forecasting etc.

SOIL Health mission: Karnataka Government has initiated program on SOIL Health mission which aims to analyse the testing of soil samples and suitable recommendations are given to the concerned farmers at right time to enable them for maintaining soil fertility.

NGOs: There are multiple number of Non-Government Organisations working on to save Indian farmers and to create awareness among farming community.

Farmer's Portal: Government of India has launched farmers' portal –one stop shop for farmers– through which a farmer can easily access all information required for a farmer such as varieties of crop, fertilisers, market price, minimum support price, soil and weather advisor, storage, insurance, farm machinery etc. relevant to the specific location.

Other Projects: Multiple schemes are announced by Government of India time to time such as Kisan Credit card, loan waiver scheme, Gramina Beej Yojana, Gramina Bhandaran Yojna, Agriculture insurance scheme, Rashtriya krishi Yojana, Krishi Vigyana Kendra, National food security mission, Agriculture Technology management, etc.

Digital platforms: The effective way of spreading knowledge is through digital platforms and also local knowledge hubs on practices relating to climate adaptation and agricultural related expertise to rural communities in India like ClimaAdapt project by NIBIO (Royal Norwegian Embassy, New Delhi)

CONCLUSION

Along with all the measures to share essential information to farmers, India has a long term strategic vision for Agriculture. But farmers are expected to participate more by making use of information available in various platforms. The Agriculture empowerment is possible when we have quality infrastructure, education, R&D, technology, marketing and risk mitigation etc.

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